

IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF TRAINING LAWYERS AND IMPROVING THEIR QUALIFICATIONS

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Annotation: The article deals with important information about developing the organizational and legal basis of training lawyers and improving their qualification. In addition to this the latest reforms according to this issue in Uzbekistan were noted.

Key words: *constitutional rights, radical modernization, non-interference, legal reforms, jurisprudence, logical structures, advanced training.*

Nowadays, for any state, the promotion isn't as it were an institution for the security of human rights and organizations, but too an important member within the arrangement of respectful society. In numerous ways, backing contributes to raising the level of legitimate mindfulness and legitimate culture of the populace. Hence, the adequacy of legitimate control of advocates' exercises specifically influences the usage of sacred rights and opportunities of the person. In this respect, it is the protected guarantee of the freedom of the promotion that's most critical.

It is not surprising that the new Uzbekistan's strategically important development program Action Strategy identifies ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial and legal system as the second priority area. Indeed, in the radical modernization of the state and society, it is essential to ensure

reliable protection of citizens' rights and freedoms, ensure the independence of the judiciary, achieve justice, strengthen the rule of law, and effectively combat corruption[1]. Within the past 2020, Uzbekistan and all circles carried out large-scale work in this course. As portion of the sacred change in Uzbekistan, it is proposed to solidify the standards of independence and self-government, non-interference within the proficient activity of an advocate. These standards are critical within the setting of progressing legal and lawful changes. Hence, within the Strategy of Activities for the Advance Advancement of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026 as the foremost important goal inside the system of the course of ensuring the run the show of law and fortifying equity, “a cardinal increment within the capacity of the founded of backing within the security of human rights, flexibilities and true blue interests” is demonstrated.

The transition to the latest digital technologies in jurisprudence does not imply a purely online format for the work of lawyers. The digital age is the era of verbal communication. That is, the ability to present their expert opinion in an understandable and accessible way becomes popular in the labor market. This increases the speed of decision making[2]. The speed and resources of search, selection and analysis of information also change, which requires a new generation of lawyers to be able to analyze large data arrays and build them into logical structures. Thus, modern lawyers should skillfully combine both traditional and innovative aspects of the profession. The digitization of the economy, according to experts, can lead to the fact that a significant part of the work of lawyers will be successfully performed by robots. Modern digital technologies provide new tools for the development of universities and other educational institutions around the world. Digitalization provides opportunities for sharing lessons learned and knowledge. Electronic Learning (e-Learning), that is, a system for training trainees, using digital technologies, information resources and Internet space, is becoming increasingly widespread. For higher education

institutions training future lawyers, the introduction of digital technology is extremely important in connection with the transition to a digital economy. In the transition to information technology of training of future lawyers in the wake of the digital economy, it is important to ensure the interaction of the various components of the educational process so that they become more dynamic, flexible and adaptive.

The advancement of data advances within the world as a entire, counting within the lawful circle, predetermines the ought to alter the approaches to preparing legal counselors. The change of instructive innovations ought to go in three headings: 1) the introduction of unused data advances into the instructive prepare at the university, which can offer assistance future attorneys to urge those competencies that will be valuable to them within the calling. At the same time, such presentation ought to concern the application of advances as of now inside the system of existing disciplines[3]. For case, these are the presentation of online courses, the utilize of uncommon programs, etc., and the presentation of modern courses into the educational prepare pointed at considering new legal relations emerging with the presentation of data innovations. The moment is preparing in data innovations and legitimate relations with their use of as of now existing legal counselors within the system of progressed preparing, which can permit them to move forward their proficient abilities. Third, the preparing of instructors themselves expect unused advances that they can actualize within the learning handle.

Today, special services are being created for lawyers that allow you to search, link, categorize, filter and track the legal information they need in their work. Legal Tech in this segment is usually called management or timeline based software, and the segment itself is called management. A new generation lawyer is able to understand the main categories of the digital economy. In this regard, in the educational process it is necessary to form with future lawyers an objective

understanding of crypt occurrences and the block chain concept, advantages, disadvantages and risks associated with their use. According to experts, the most important functions of a lawyer include analysis, prediction of the situation and the search for optimal solutions. And they can also be automated with the help of artificial intelligence technologies, which will allow you to predict the scenarios and outcome of each specific case, prepare a legal opinion or quickly find the necessary information. So, for example, obtaining students digital competencies in the field of forensics is important for the successful investigation of crimes[4].

Summing up all given realities it ought to be famous that backing is the foremost critical legitimate institution of any state, standing for the assurance of the basic rights of citizens and their affiliations. The certainty of each citizen or business visionary in their well-being and victory to a great extent depends on how solid, organized, and lawfully ensured it is. In this manner, sacred ensures of freedom and self-government are vital both for the advocates themselves and for society.

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